

carbazole alkaloid of the same plant using the above thermal method of synthesis.

The starting diphenylamine, 4'-methoxy-4-methyl-diphenylamine (V), m.p. 122°-23°, was synthesised from *p*-toluidine hydrochloride and *p*-anisidine. The diphenylamine derivative was then heated in a sealed tube at 350° in presence of iodine for 3 hr. After the reaction was complete, the product was taken up in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. From the reaction mixture a compound m.p. 181°-82° was obtained which was found to be identical with natural glycozoline (IV) (i.r., u.v., m.m.p.).

- I, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$
 V, $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = CH_3$; $R_3 = OCH_3$
 II, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$
 III, $R_1 = R_3 = OCH_3$; $R_2 = CH_3$
 IV, $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = CH_3$; $R_3 = OCH_3$

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether had the boiling point 60°-80° unless otherwise mentioned. For chromatography (tlc and column) silica gel supplied by Gouri Chemical, Calcutta and alumina of M/s. Saiabhai Merck, India were used.

4'-Methoxy-4-methyl diphenylamine (V) :

p-Toluidine hydrochloride (500 mg) was mixed with *p*-anisidine (1 g) and heated at 270° for 4 hr. After the reaction the product was taken up in ethyl acetate, it was washed with 1% HCl and then with water and dried over anh. Na_2SO_4 . It was then filtered, the solvent distilled and the residue taken in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. The petroleum ether benzene (1 : 1) eluent furnished (V), in a crystalline form, m.p. 122°-23°. Yield 200 mg. [Found : C, 78.80; H, 7.0; N, 6.55%; requires C, 78.94; H, 7.09; N, 6.57%] λ_{max}^{EtOH} 272, 263, 232 nm with $\log \epsilon$ 4.58, 4.60, 4.32; ν_{max}^{NaCl} 3450, 1620, 1520, 1470, 1300 cm^{-1} .

Glycozoline (IV) :

Diphenylamine (V; 100 mg) was heated in a sealed tube at 350° in presence of a trace amount of iodine for 3 hr. After this, the reaction product was taken in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. The benzene eluent furnished a solid which melted at 181° and was identical with natural glycozoline (ur, ir, mmp). Yield 20 mg.

References

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Formation Constants and Thermodynamic Study of Tl(I)-3-Nitro-Salicylates

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THE formation constants of Tl(I)-3NSA have been determined *pH*-metrically, employing half-integral method (HI), described by Irving and Rossotti¹. Refined values of formation constants are then obtained by linear-plot (LP), point-wise calculation (PC) and least square (LS) methods at three different temperatures, viz., 30°, 35° and 40°. The thermodynamic parameters, ΔF , ΔH , and ΔS , have also been calculated.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of Analar B.D.H. grade.

Polymetron model CL-41 *pH*-meter was used for *pH*-metric titrations conducted at 30°, 35° and 40°. Measurements were made with an accuracy of ± 0.05 *pH* unit and the reproducibility of the readings was of the same order. The *pH*-meter was calibrated using Cambridge buffer tablets of *pH* 4.01 and 9.11.

pH-Metric titrations of the solutions of (i) free $HClO_4$, (ii) free $HClO_4 + 3$ -NSA and (iii) free $HClO_4 + 3$ -NSA + Tl(I) were performed in 50% (v/v) aqueous-ethanol medium against standard NaOH solution while maintaining the ionic strength at 0.1M ($NaClO_4$).

The experimental set up and the method of calculation is the same as described earlier²⁻⁴.

Results and Discussion

The Irving-Rossotti expression¹ was used for the calculations of \bar{n} and *p*(L). The proton-ligand formation constants of 3-NSA, as reported earlier⁵, under the same experimental conditions, were used for the calculation of *p*(L). In calculating \bar{n} and *p*(L) the concentrations were corrected for the changes in volume as a result of addition of alkali during titration. A series of values of \bar{n} and *p*(L) corresponding to different B-values (*pH*-meter reading) were calculated and formation curves obtained by plotting \bar{n} versus *p*(L) (Fig. 1). The \bar{n} values never exceed 1.7 indicating thereby, the formation of only 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by half-integral method (HI) making use of formation curves. The values of *p*(L) at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 correspond to the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ respectively. Refined values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were also obtained using afore

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TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Tl(I)-3-NITRO SALICYLATES

Method	30°			35°			40°		
	log K_1	log K_2	log B_2	log K_1	log K_2	log B_2	log K_1	log K_2	log B_2
HI	7.91	5.12	13.03	7.32	4.57	11.89	6.56	4.70	11.26
LP	7.90	5.11	13.01	7.25	4.57	11.82	6.53	4.65	11.18
PC	7.87	5.01	12.88	7.31	4.45	11.76	6.66	4.38	11.04
LS	7.80	5.01	12.81	7.27	4.26	11.53	6.69	4.25	10.94
Average	7.87	5.05	12.81	7.29	4.46	11.75	6.60	4.60	11.10

mentioned methods and are recorded in Table 1. The values of formation constants are concentration stability constants. Although the values obtained

average value is recorded in Table 2. The values of ΔS were then evaluated from the relation

$$\Delta S = \Delta H - \Delta F/T$$

and are recorded in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Formation Curves of Tl(I)-3-Nitro Salicylates

○ 30°C; △ 35°C; □ 40°C.

by the method of least-square would be more acceptable, it may be seen that these values as determined by other methods are also representative values of the formation constants.

Perusal of Table 1 shows that the ratio $\log K_1/K_2$ is positive and that the separation factor between first and second formation constants is well within the expected range. A bigger difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ and a high value of $\log K_1/K_2$ is because of possible steric hindrance on the linking of the second ligand molecule expected for Tl(I) ion.

The values of change in free energy (ΔF), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for the complexation reaction have been determined applying the standard equations. The values of ΔH is determined by temperature co-efficient method as well as from the isobar.

$$\frac{d \ln K_n}{dT} = \Delta H/RT^2$$

which can be written as

$$\frac{d(\log K_n)}{d(1/T)} = \Delta H/4.57.$$

The values of $\log K_n$ were plotted as a function of $1/T$ and the gradient of the tangent was equated to $-\Delta H/4.57$ and thus ΔH was found in K.cal., the

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR Tl(I)-3-NITRO SALICYLATES

Temp.	$-\Delta F_1$ (K.cal./mole)	$-\Delta F_2$ (K.cal./mole)	$-\Delta H_1$ (K.cal./mole)	$-\Delta H_2$ (K.cal./mole)	$-\Delta S_1$ (e.u.)	$-\Delta S_2$ (e.u.)
30°	14.77	10.98			46.57	14.55
35°	14.22	10.34	28.88	55.09	47.60	14.53
40°	13.96	9.53			47.60	14.55

The formation of Tl(I)-3NSA is a spontaneous process which is evident from free energy value. The negative values of ΔH ensures that the reaction is exothermic and metal-ligand bond is stronger than the ligand-solvent bond. The negative values of ΔS indicate that the products are more ordered than the reactants.

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Studies in Oxadiazoles. Part III. Synthesis of Some Basic N-(5-Aryl-1,3,4-Oxadiazol-2-yl) Acetamides

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BASIC acetamides, in which amido-H has been substituted with aromatic¹ or heterocyclic² moieties have been synthesised in large number as potential local anaesthetics. Of these Lidocaine¹